

Practice Guidelines for the Care of Patients Undergoing Mandibular Distraction Osteogenesis

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Background

Robin Sequence (RS)

- 1 in 8,500 live births
- Micrognathia (small-receded mandible)
- Glossoptosis (posterior placement of the tongue)
- Airway obstruction & cleft palate may occur

Mandibular Distraction Osteogenesis (MDO)

- Mandibular osteotomy and placement of distraction devices
- Short period of healing
- Distractors are activated and the osteotomy is opened 1.8 mm each day
- Tongue moves forward and the airway opens
- Consolidation phase follows; ossification of the mandible occurs
- No existing practice standards for infants undergoing MDO
- Current hospital stays are long and care is fragmented
- Family & staff education is needed

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this DNP project was to develop a set of standardized practice guidelines for the post-surgical care of patients undergoing Mandibular Distraction Osteogenesis (MDO).

Methods

Evidence-based strategies and expert opinion were utilized throughout the process

- Children's Hospital Los Angeles has historically endorsed the concept of family centered care
- Care was provided in the newborn and infant critical care unit (NICCU)
- Guidelines were developed for children < 6 months with airway obstruction caused by micrognathia
- Stakeholders included a multidisciplinary team of providers and families of patients who have had MDO

Framework

Revised Iowa Model: Steps One to Five

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Implementation Plan

- Pilot clinical care guidelines with two patients
- Revise guidelines based upon stakeholders' input
- Provide education to parents & nurses
- Edit educational materials based upon feedback
- Guidelines will become the standard of care
- Incorporate RS MDO guidelines into the facility's EHR
- Ongoing evaluation will take place

Discussion

- Management of complex patients with RS requires clear guidelines to mitigate variability in care and for attaining optimal outcomes
- Involvement of the multidisciplinary team and family is essential
- A nurse driven process was key in both the coordination and development of the MDO guidelines
- The resulting MDO guidelines represent a comprehensive effort by all of the key stakeholders

Conclusion

Evidence-based interdisciplinary clinical practice guidelines directing the care of children with RS who undergo MDO will likely:

- Improve patient outcomes and patient/family quality of life
 - ↑ parental involvement
 - ↓ parental anxiety
- Lead to a more timely transition to oral feedings
- ↓ hospital length of stay
- ↓ hospital costs and resources
- Improve quality and timeliness of follow-up care

"I do think that mandibular distraction has to be in the top 10 procedural innovations to impact the care of babies in the last decade or so. The care of babies with severe micrognathia has been completely transformed by it!"

William Benitz, MD, Professor and Chief of Neonatal-Perinatal Medicine, Stanford Children's Hospital